

Auditing what the algorithm pays attention to at the time of war : How image search framed the Russian-Ukrainian war before and after the 2022 invasion

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1. Introduction

Search engines serve as key information intermediaries in today's high-choice media environment. By selecting and ranking textual and visual content in response to user queries, search engines help individuals navigate the abundance of information available online and determine what individuals' attention will be focused on. In this way, search algorithms shape social reality by making certain aspects of specific phenomena, such as race (Noble, 2018) or mass atrocities, more salient than others. Consequently, algorithms that power search engines become crucial elements of the contemporary digital ecosystem, affecting how specific phenomena - including the ongoing mass violence in Eastern Europe and the Middle East - are presented to and interpreted by the digital public.

Despite the growing recognition of the importance of search engines as framing actors (e.g., Arendt, 2018), the way their algorithms make decisions about the representation of individual phenomena remains understudied. Partially, this is due to the notorious lack of transparency of algorithmic mechanisms behind the search engines, which are increasingly powered by artificial intelligence that is used to process billions of web pages and personalize their selection for individual users, taking into consideration hundreds of possible variables (e.g. user location, search language, or history of earlier searches). In particular, there is limited understanding of how framing decisions are affected by the user- (e.g., the query formulation; Van Hoof et al., 2022) and system-side factors (e.g., changes in content relevance over time; Lewandowski, 2008).

To investigate how search algorithms frame wars and whether their representation of violence is subjected to certain forms of bias, we analyze how two Western (i.e., Google and Bing) and one Russian (i.e., Yandex) search engines visually frame the ongoing Russian-Ukrainian war. Our interest in this case study is attributed to this war being the largest conflict in Europe since the 1990s and also the one accompanied by the intense epistemic contestation of the different aspects of the mass violence (e.g., Tyushka, 2023). This epistemic contestation makes the unbiased algorithmic representation of mass violence more challenging, as the search algorithms need to make ontological choices regarding what interpretations or sources to prioritise. The change in the dynamic of the war, which escalated in 2022 following the large-scale Russian invasion and the dramatic increase in the number of deaths and war crimes, poses another challenge that search algorithms have to accommodate.

In our study, we specifically focus on image search and visual framing. This focus is attributed to the effectiveness of visual content in communicating information about mass violence to the public

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(e.g., Parry, 2010; Makhortykh and Sydorova, 2017). Images are a powerful framing device in this context, both due to their interlocutory potential that allows them to describe phenomena that are hard to represent verbally (Bleiker, 2018) and their capacities for stirring and articulating emotions. However, these features also make images more likely to be used for manipulating public opinion and propagating hate speech as part of the epistemic contestation of mass violence. These risks are further amplified by the evidence of image search algorithms being particularly prone to misrepresentation of contested phenomena, especially in the form of the discriminatory treatment of vulnerable groups (e.g., Kay et al., 2015; Noble, 2018). Against this backdrop, we ask the following research questions: How do Western and non-Western search engines visually frame the Russian-Ukrainian war? Is their framing subject to certain forms of bias regarding the visibility and invisibility of specific actors and aspects of violence? And how such framing and associated biases are influenced by the system- (e.g., time) and user-side (e.g., language) factors?

To answer these research questions, we will use a unique longitudinal dataset regarding the search engine representation of the Russian-Ukrainian war, which we collected in 2021-2023. To collect the dataset, we used a virtual agent-based approach (Haim et al., 2017; Ulloa et al., 2024) and regularly audited the performance of Google, Yandex, and Bing for the query “war in Ukraine” in English, Ukrainian, and Russian languages in 2021, 2022, and 2023 (i.e., before and after the war’s escalation). Google and Bing are the two most commonly used search engines in the Global North, with Google being the monopolist in the majority of Global Northern search markets. By contrast, Yandex is the major search engine in Russia and a number of countries of the former Soviet bloc. There is also evidence (e.g., Kravets & Toepfl, 2022; Makhortykh et al., 2022) of Yandex being particularly prone to the influence of the Kremlin, resulting in the company adapting its algorithms to promote pro-regime sources and interpretations, which is of particular relevance for representing the Kremlin-triggered mass violence in Ukraine.

To investigate the framing of the war by search engines, we use qualitative content analysis and examine how consistent the salience of specific aspects of the war and actors is over time and whether there are substantial differences in the saliency depending on the language of the query and the choice of the search engine. Specifically, we are interested in whether the algorithms are subject to social bias, for instance, in terms of adopting the male gaze perspective on the war (i.e., by hiding the presence of women both as soldiers and civilians) and if there is systematic under- or over-representation of specific aspects of violence (e.g., combat actions or suffering of civilians) as well as whether changes over time and varies across the search engines (e.g., if after the large-scale invasion Yandex tends to promote more pro-Russian framing of the war considering its connections with Kremlin and the intensification of censorship in Russia). Currently, we have completed the analysis for 2021 and 2022, with the analysis for 2023 to be completed. Our preliminary findings indicate the surprisingly few changes in the visual framing of the war before and after the large-scale invasion, with the tendency to focus on the male actors and limited visibility of the non-military aspects of the mass violence.

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